

EVIDENCE-BASED
TOXICOLOGY

Evaluation Report

for **TEBT-2025-0009**

Submission Information Table

Submission Title	A piece of the ecotoxicology puzzle: how can current and future research inform PPD regulations?
Submission Reference	TEBT-2025-0009
Handling Editor	Paul Whaley 0000-0003-4021-0785 (current) Olwenn Martin 0000-0003-2724-7882 (previous)
Editor Declaration of Interests	The editors are not aware of any conflicts of interest that could compromise their handling of this submission.
Number of Reviewers	2 editors and 3 peer-reviewers
Submission Type	Comment
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Report Number	5
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Use of AI in evaluation	DataSeer.ai was used to check the consistency of data availability statements in the manuscript with journal policies. Prophy.ai was used to identify suitable peer-reviewers for the manuscript.

Editor's Summary of Reviewer Comments

Written by the Handling Editor as a summary of the key points from the peer-review process

This manuscript presents the authors' expert opinion on the state-of-the-art of research into the toxicity of 6PPD and 6PPD-Q, with recommendations about the type of studies that should be conducted to best support regulatory decision-making around a pollutant of increasing international concern.

In the manuscript's initial form, reviewers were not convinced of the value of a non-systematic review on a topic without a large literature and for which several reviews already exist. However, it was considered that there might be value in a review that identifies trends in research and provides expert opinion on useful directions for future work. With input from the handling editors, this led to the authors reconfiguring their manuscript into a comment article.

I am satisfied that the authors' revisions have sufficiently delivered this change in approach, with the manuscript being a potentially useful primer on recent developments in research into the toxicity of 6PPD-Q, and that it concludes with constructive suggestions about future research that would support international regulatory decision-making.

Since further revisions are unlikely to substantively improve the manuscript, I am pleased to accept this submission for publication.

Note: *The authors' responses to the final round of reviewer comments are included alongside this acceptance note on Zenodo.*

Acceptance Note

This manuscript was accepted for publication by the handling editor Paul Whaley after four rounds of review. Evaluation reports for the manuscript can be found at <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15587268>. Preprint versions of the manuscript and author responses to comments in the evaluation reports can be found at <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15186022>.